

LIDERAZGO LÍDER LIDERAR

Dra. Gloria Cristina Palos Cerda

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TEMAS DE HOY:

01 ¿QUÉ
SIGNIFICA?
(LIDERAZGO)

02 EJEMPLOS+
(LÍDER)

03 SOFT &
HARD
SKILLS
(LIDERAR)

04 TENDENCIAS
DE
LIDERAZGO
2024

01

¿QUÉ SIGNIFICA? (LIDERAZGO)

Educación
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POTOSÍ
PARA LOS POTOSINOS
GOBIERNO DEL ESTADO 2021-2027

SEGE
SECRETARÍA DE EDUCACIÓN
DE GOBIERNO DEL ESTADO

02

EJEMPLOS+ (LÍDER)

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03

SOFT & HARD SKILLS (LIDERAR)

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04 TENDENCIAS DE LIDERAZGO 2024

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THE **SLIDE** TITLE GOES HERE!

Do you know what helps you make your point clear? Lists like this:

- They're simple
- You can organize your ideas
- You'll never forget to buy milk!

And the audience won't miss the point of your presentation

1. ¿Qué es el liderazgo?
 - Quiz: una palabra que define al líder y los problemas que se enfrentan con su equipo de trabajo.
 - Definiciones y frases de liderazgo.

1. Ejemplos de líderes
 - Tipos de líderes y sus ejemplos.

1. Soft skills & hard skills.
 - Definiciones y matriz para identificarlas.
 - Herramientas para líderes

1. Tendencias de liderazgo

“This is a quote, words full of wisdom that someone important said and can make the reader get inspired”

—**SOMEONE FAMOUS**

WHAT ABOUT THESE TWO CONCEPTS?

MERCURY

It's the closest planet to the Sun and the smallest one in the Solar System

VENUS

Venus has a beautiful name and is the second planet from the Sun

THREE COLUMNS

MARS

Despite being red, Mars is a very cold place

VENUS

Venus is the second planet from the Sun

NEPTUNE

Neptune is the farthest from the Sun

AWESOME WORDS

A PICTURE ALWAYS REINFORCES THE CONCEPT

Images reveal large amounts of data, so remember: use an image instead of a long text

OUR DATA

JUPITER 25%

It's the biggest planet in the Solar System

MARS 25%

Despite being red, Mars is a cold place

VENUS 40%

Venus is the second planet from the Sun

Follow the link in the graph to modify its data and then paste the new one here. **For more info, click here**

REVIEWING CONCEPTS IS GOOD

MERCURY

Mercury is the closest to the Sun

VENUS

Venus is the second planet from the Sun

MARS

Despite being red, Mars is a cold place

SATURN

Saturn is a gas giant and has several rings

NEPTUNE

Neptune is the farthest from the Sun

JUPITER

It's the biggest planet in the Solar System

**A PICTURE IS
WORTH A
THOUSAND
WORDS**

THIS IS AN INFOGRAPHIC

MARS

Despite being red, Mars is a cold place

VENUS

Venus is the second planet from the Sun

NEPTUNE

Neptune is the farthest from the Sun

JUPITER

It's the biggest planet in the Solar System

THIS IS A TABLE

MARS

Despite being red,
Mars is a cold place

MERCURY

Mercury is the
closest to the Sun

VENUS

Venus is the second
planet from the Sun

AND THIS IS A MAP

VENUS

Venus is the second planet from the Sun

SATURN

Saturn is a gas giant and has several rings

4,980

Big numbers catch your audience's attention

A TIMELINE ALWAYS WORKS WELL

THIS IS A CALENDAR

JULY

MO	TU	WE	TH	FR	SA	SU
			1	2	3	4
5	6	7	8	9	10	11
12	13	14	15	16	17	18
19	20	21	22	23	24	25
26	27	28	29	30	31	

JULY 4TH

Venus is the second planet from the Sun

333,000.00

earths is the Sun's mass

9h 55m 23s

is Jupiter's rotation period

386,000 km

is a very long distance

ANOTHER GRAPH

VENUS

Venus is the second planet from the Sun

MARS

Despite being red, Mars is a cold place

Follow the link in the graph to modify its data and then paste the new one here. **For more info, click here**

THESE ARE SOME PERCENTAGES

34%

MERCURY

Mercury is the closest to the Sun

67%

MARS

Despite being red, Mars is a cold place

THIS IS ANOTHER TABLE

○

01	02	03	04
Mercury is the smallest planet in the Solar System	Jupiter is the biggest planet in the Solar System	Venus has a beautiful name, but it's very hot	It's composed of hydrogen and helium

○

THIS IS A DIAGRAM

MERCURY

1

2021

Mercury is the closest planet to the Sun

2

2022

It's the biggest planet in the Solar System

3

2023

Venus has a beautiful name, but it's hot

NEED MORE COLUMNS OF TEXT?

VENUS

Venus is the second planet from the Sun

JUPITER

It's the biggest planet in the Solar System

MERCURY

Mercury is the closest to the Sun

MARS

Despite being red, Mars is a cold place

OUR CONCLUSIONS

MERCURY

Mercury is the closest to the Sun

VENUS

Venus is the second planet from the Sun

MARS

Despite being red, Mars is a cold place

OUR TEAM

**JENNA
McKANE**

You can replace the
image on the screen
with your own

**JOHN
DOE**

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image on the screen
with your own

DESKTOP SOFTWARE

You can replace the image on the screen with your own work. Just delete this one, add yours and center it properly

TABLET APP

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MOBILE WEB

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THANKS!

Do you have any questions?
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ALTERNATIVE RESOURCES

PHOTOS:

- Medium shot team leader posing
- Front view people meeting cup coffee
- Business people meeting office working
- Young business people working laptop
- Front view smiley people meeting
- People social distancing work
- Business people meeting office
- Man having video call work

RESOURCES

VECTORS:

- General business horizontal banner template

PHOTOS:

- Young business woman checking her tablet with copy space
- Medium shot people meeting
- Medium shot business woman with post-its
- Teamwork meeting with business people

- Business woman with tablet
- Man woman discussing business project
- Medium shot happy business people
- Medium shot woman talking business
- Business meeting office working
- Corporate workers brainstorming
- Entrepreneurs meeting office
- Business people meeting office
- Young business people working
- Business people meeting office
- Woman showing something

RESOURCES

- Smiley colleagues office during meeting
- Medium shot team members together
- Portrait young businessman working
- Portrait smiley business woman

